
Exploring Hotel's Corporate Social Responsibility and Community Development in Adamawa Metropolis, Nigeria- A Critical Review

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Abstract

Several academics regard Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) as a useful business tool utilized by hotels to incorporate social and environmental concerns into their daily operations. CSR is built on the hotel industry's moral culture for community and environmental sustainability, as well as maintaining the interests of its stakeholders. In Nigeria, the hotel business has also absorbed social issues and embraced CSR strategies of helping disadvantaged communities, increasing diversity among its staff, and improving employment culture; Transcorp Hilton Abuja is a pioneer leader in this arena. This study analyzed the body of available literature on the extent of a hotel's CSR efforts that may affect community development in the Adamawa Metropolis in Nigeria. It became evident that a company's ability to properly manage connections with key constituencies such as customers, employees, communities and even stakeholders is critical to its success. It was discovered that the hotel organization's decision-making process must take stakeholders into account. CSR is a broad concept that incorporates a wide range of activities and actions that businesses must conduct in order to thrive, sustain, and expand their operations.

1. Introduction

The term "corporate social responsibility" (CSR) refers to an organization's civic duty to the community in which it is headquartered and, in certain other ways, to the society at large (Samer et al., 2018). In a mutually beneficial, synergistic, and symbiotic relationship, it also provides a company with a way to give back to the society and host communities from which it has benefited. Welfare initiatives, including the provision of portable drinking water, high-quality medical treatment, rural electrification, affordable housing, education, the upgrading/provision of school facilities, the beautifying of streets and highways, among other things, are used to achieve this goal. The business sector possesses the requisite human resources, financial capital, and physical resources to contribute to community development, claim Celik & Abdul-kareem (2019). highlighting the fact that corporate executives,

academics, and society at general have all given the idea of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) a lot of attention during the past few decades.

Due to the complexity of the business world, the growing concern for sustainable development, the need for ethical behavior, and the call for better transparency, corporate social responsibility (CSR) is becoming more and more integrated into company operations (Amsami et al., 2020). The four categories of CSR are philanthropic, ethical, legal, and economic, according to Carroll's (1991) paradigm. CSR procedures must therefore be fully implemented by corporations if they are to satisfy all stakeholders and give back to the community (Bello et al., 2017). According to Singal Manisha and Rhou Yinyoung (2017), this approach will benefit a firm in both good and bad times. A number of recent studies, including Banks et al. (2016), Fung Wong & Kim (2000), Rhou & Singal (2000), and others have shown that the importance of CSR in community development cannot be overstated; as a result, the majority of developed and developing countries view CSR as the means of eradicating poverty, enhancing individual welfare, and a duty to ensure the survival and economic prosperity of the community (Raimi et al., 2019). Yet, empirical research has indicated that there is a paucity of information surrounding this topic in Nigeria (Yusuf et al., 2017).

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a tool used by businesses and other corporate entities in Nigeria to interact with their clients and the environment (Joy et al., 2022). While some businesses have designated education as one of their Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) platforms, supporting educational advancement through sponsorships by giving out scholarships and improving general school facilities, others have lent a hand in supporting the improvement of public infrastructure, such as roads and other feasible/valuable projects (Etekpe, 2021). A business entity must first decide the platform it wants to use to interact with its host community in order to optimize the value of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) to the community and the accompanying goodwill for the organization. The demands that have been identified ought to drive this. The identified and pressing needs of the people should be the driving force behind this. Collaboration with stakeholders can be used to identify such needs, which must have a long-term impact on people's lives, for a positive experience for everybody (Etekpe, 2021)

Today, corporate social responsibility (CSR) is a major focus for hospitality businesses all over the world as a means of strengthening stakeholder relationships and enhancing operational efficiency. With its significance for both the economy and the environment, the hotel industry is one of the most obvious potential customers for CSR initiatives (Ampofo, 2020). This strategy, which hoteliers believe is necessary to achieve long-term growth and profitability, is causing them growing amounts of concern. Babajee et al. (2022) claim that there has recently been a lot of pressure on hotels to act in a socially and environmentally responsible way in order to allay environmental concerns and meet community needs.

Abram and Jarzbek (2016) stated further that hotels must match societal expectations while minimizing adverse effects on the environment, assisting their staff, and contributing to the local community. Corporate Social Responsibility has thus become a crucial area of concern for company executives around the world (Wong & Kim, 2023). Despite recent developments in the industry, there is still a very low level of knowledge of corporate social responsibility (CSR) in Nigeria's hospitality and tourism sector in general and the hotel industry in particular. According to a survey of the literature, scientific research into CSR in the hotel industry began in the middle of 2000 and has continued to grow ever since. Regrettably, there hasn't been a thorough study done exclusively for CSR and community development in the hotel industry, especially in Adamawa metropolitan. Hence, the need for this research

The paper is broken up into four parts, excluding the introduction. The general concept of CSR is covered in the first part. This part of the debate is crucial because it will show how CSR requires businesses and organizations to view their obligations in a broader context that includes not only stakeholders but also a wide range of other constituencies, such as the community where their operations are located. The second part of the paper examines empirical studies that have been done on the subject under discussion. The theoretical framework for the investigation is discussed in the third section. The conclusion and recommendation are the focus of the fourth part. Given that the issues raised in this study may make it difficult to apply CSR effectively, this section offered some recommendations.

Figure 1: Pyramid of CSR

Source: Ikhana, 2022

Carroll identified four CSR sectors in the 1990s and then created the CSR pyramid. Carroll (1991) claimed that the pyramid shows what is expected of the company. According to him, the idea of corporate citizenship suggests that businesses put the interests of the community first and treat those interests in the same manner they treat their own. In the 1990s, multinational corporations started to gain popularity. These corporations looked at moral principles, community concerns, human rights, and environmental issues (Ikhana, 2022)

2. Conceptual Literature

Corporate Social Responsibility

E. Merrick Dodd invented the phrase "corporate social responsibility" in 1932. According to Bowen, the "father of CSR," business has a responsibility to pursue organizational policies and make choices that are desirable in terms of social objectives. Also, it is commonly known

that strategic CSR can enhance competitive advantage because doing good works benefits both a firm and society.

CSR is defined as "a process companies use to integrate social, environmental, ethical, human rights, and consumer concerns into their business operations... with the aim of maximizing the creation of shared value for their owners/shareholders, for their other stakeholders, and for society at large," according to the European Commission (2011), as cited in González-rodriguez et al. (2019). According to the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) (2017), corporate social responsibility (CSR) refers to an organization's pledge to support economic growth that is sustainable by working with its workforce, their families, the community, and society at large to raise everyone's standard of living. Stakeholder theory views CSR as highlighting the significance of all stakeholders, not only the owners, investors, and shareholders. Observing ethical, social, and economic standards. The corporation must involve all of its target audiences in order to uphold environmental, social, and economic principles because carrying out CSR initiatives will depend on the expectations of each relevant group (Wang et al., 2019)

The definition of CSR created by the International Organization for Standardization is the most typical and widely referenced definition (ISO). Corporate social responsibility is defined by the ISO 26000 standard as the "responsibility of an organization for the impacts of its decisions and activities on society and the environment through transparent and ethical behavior that contributes to sustainable development, including health and the welfare of society; takes into account the expectations of stakeholders; is in compliance with applicable law and consistent with international norms of behavior, and is in compliance with applicable law and international norms of behavior (Abram & Jarzabek, 2016).

Masum et al. (2020) define corporate social responsibility (CSR) as a business strategy that uses ethical systems and sustainable management techniques to apply and integrate the generation and distribution of wealth for the benefit of its stakeholders. In other words, CSR refers to strategies used by businesses or organizations to conduct operations in a moral, sociable, and developmentally beneficial way. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) was described by Abram and Jarzbek (2016) as a management strategy in which businesses voluntarily take into account the social and environmental impacts of their operations. The cornerstone of CSR is acting morally and responsibly toward all stakeholders while safeguarding the environment. Large organizations especially multinational corporations at first showed interest in the idea of corporate social responsibility. Small and medium-sized firms, organizations, and management theorists are now interested in CSR. The strategy introduces new competitive opportunities while allowing them to operate consistently and effectively (Abram & Jarzbek, 2016).

Celik & Abdul-kareem (2019) define CSR as the responsibility of a firm to respond to the requirements of its stakeholders in its operations and to take into account not just the

financial element of decision-making but also the social and environmental repercussions. Business organizations utilize CSR as a means of managing and upholding a balance between the economic, environmental, and social obligations they have to the community. According to them, CSR can be employed as a tactical maneuver to cope with societal forces that have a propensity to obstruct the achievement of organizational goals.

CSR is often referred to as society's expectations of firms at any given time in terms of their economic, legal, ethical, and discretionary behavior. The idea of CSR emphasizes that businesses have duties that go beyond generating a fair return for investors and abiding with the law, such as moral, ethical, and charitable obligations (Hakeem Ijaiya, 2014). According to Kumari et al. (2017), corporate social responsibility (CSR) is the duty to improve community well-being through optional business practices and corporate resource influences. Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is simply defined by Fung Wong & Kim (2020) as the way in which a company conducts its operations while accepting accountability for its impact on society.

A hotel that uses a triple-bottom-line strategy to consider people, planet, and profit in all aspects of its operations and is accountable for its societal acts (community), is known as having a hotel CSR. This definition is based on the several definitions that were previously presented. Environmental concerns, respect for local populations, the use of technology, and energy usage are further characteristics of CSR. Raimi et al. (2019) stated that academic scholars' and practitioners' definitions of CSR defined it as firms' attention to the concerns and expectations of their host communities above and beyond the bare minimum duties imposed by law. Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is a management concept that has been more well-known during the past 10 years in a variety of company sectors, according to Sran Bogeti and Zorana Anti (2017). The hotel industry is one of the most obvious prospective industries given its effects on the economy and environment. The hotel industry is one of the most obvious potential consumers of the application of CSR principles due to its effects on the economy and environment.

Community Development Concept

For the purpose of this study, we have used the United Nations' commonly accepted definition of community development. The United Nations defines "community development" as an endeavor by individuals in a community to handle community problems with the least amount of assistance from outside organizations. External organizations include government and non-government organizations, as well as corporations of various sizes and sorts, such as small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and multinational corporations. The implication of the UN concept of community development is thus to emphasize innovation and self-reliance in the community for short and long term goals, but not to contradict the many forms of corporate firms' CSR roles. The history of community development dates back to the dawn of humankind, when farming methods and fire were

developed. All initiatives to enhance this quality of life could be categorized as community development. Hence, community development might be defined as the improvement of an individual's, society's, and political economy's well-being. In this regard, it is crucial to comprehend the issues at hand by reviewing pertinent literature. In Adamawa State, Wakili (2013) cited in Yusuf et al., (2017) evaluated how the Local Empowerment and Environmental Management Programme (LEEMP) affected rural community development. The socioeconomic standing of some of the beneficiary communities in nine (9) Local Government Areas of the State was evaluated by his study. 30 communities were chosen using a straightforward random selection procedure.

With most studies on CSR starting from a corporate standpoint and encouraged by 'the claim...that it is lucrative to behave well', Banks et al., (2016) states that business has become a 'proactive player in defining and disseminating the CSR agenda'. As a result, one of the main criticisms of CSR is that it puts corporate companies' goals and perspectives ahead of the communities who are supposed to gain from it. In an environment where there are rising expectations for the private sector to engage more fully in development efforts, there is a need for improved knowledge of the limitations to what large firms can accomplish while "doing community development". Many developmental effects that companies have are both deliberate and unintended. These effects include a variety of causes, including the neoliberal environment, community interactions and agency, and corporate objectives. The CSR lens, which is business-oriented, falls short of capturing all of these benefits both empirically (as that lens does not systematically look for any of these effects) (Banks et al., 2016).

The Hotel Industry in Nigeria

In Nigeria, the hotel industry is one of the government's priority areas for stimulating economic growth, creating job opportunities, and generating foreign exchange. While the evolution of hospitality in Nigeria is in stages, formal evidence of the industry's growth is limited due to inadequate record maintenance, as in many other early businesses in Nigeria. The establishment of catering guest houses by the government in the 1920s (via Nigeria Railway Caterers Limited) and other catering guest houses across Nigeria in the 1950s marked the beginning of what would later become the nucleus of Nigeria's formal hospitality trade (National Association of Nigeria Travel Agencies: AGM/Conference 2001). The first hospitality businesses in Nigeria were created and run by government and were placed in large seaports, railway termini, or major towns where state capitals were located. The European Rest House at Port Harcourt and the Lagos Rest House were established in 1923 and 1931, respectively (Federal Government of Nigeria Reports on National Hotels Classification and Grading Exercise 1989:67). The creation of institutions such as hotels, guest houses, staff canteens, and staff clubs is the next most important development phase of the hospitality business in Nigeria. Hospitality concerns in Nigeria were primarily

government-driven until 2001, when President Obasanjo's administration took over(Olabinjo et al., 2020).

CSR Initiative in Nigeria

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) programs were developed in Nigeria as a result of multinational corporations' (MNCs) activities in the country's extractive industries, particularly the oil industry. Its activities in local communities led to CSR violations like oil spills, gas flare-ups, militancy/community unrest, and the dumping of toxic waste into rivers. Due to the destruction of the communities' primary economic drivers farming and fishing which resulted in severe poverty and community unrest. These factors taken together prompted questions regarding the place of businesses in Nigerian society(Amodu,2021). In addition to MNCs' activities, the failure of successive Nigerian governments to fulfill their mandate to provide social amenities for communities has transformed MNCs into quasi-governments that focus on and depend on the local community(Osemeke et al., 2016) In addition to MNCs' operations, successive Nigerian governments have fallen short of their obligations by relying on and favoring MNCs to address their economic issues. Government at all levels has fallen short in providing remedies (such as building infrastructures, roads, medical equipment and schools). This is mostly a result of corruption, a lackluster institutional setup, a lack of accountability and openness among public officials, among other problems (Osakwe & Yusuf, 2021)

The result is that CSR initiatives in Nigeria have not been strategically oriented, in a way that fully engages businesses in society and nation building, but rather have been culturally oriented, reflecting the religion, ethnicity, traditions, and communal lifestyle of the people that involves sharing, togetherness, and consensus(Etekpe, 2021). As a result, CSR projects in Nigeria have largely been philanthropic. The majority of corporate entities, including MNCs and financial institutions, are serious about CSR projects. Some businesses publish their environmental and CSR reports in addition to their annual reports and have CSR divisions(Osemeke et al., 2016). Its CSR initiatives focus mostly on project implementation, donation giving, road beautification, and sports sponsorship. The supply of borehole water, youth empowerment, schools, and healthcare facilities for the communities are a few of these programs(Bello et al., 2017)

Impact of CSR on Community Development

The impact of CSR on community development in the context of this study encompasses any direct and indirect advantages received by the community as a result of hotels' social commitment to the wider community and social system. Cherapanukorn & Focken (2014)suggested that it was time for the hospitality industry to be practical and live up to the expectations to be hospitable and to care for immediate world. According to the authors,

there is a prevailing awareness of the necessity and benefits; however, it seems to be unclear how to integrate the activities into the core business and how to demonstrate real impacts and positive changes

According to a study by Masum et al., (2020), hotels' CSR generally has the following effects on community development:

- Hotels' CSR strengthens links between corporations and the community. By engaging in CSR activities, hotels' existence in the social system is felt beyond the assumption that corporations are only places to acquire jobs and manufacturers of goods and services. Corporations and communities would remain in peace and harmony as a result. This creates social capital, which is critical for community growth.
- The implementation of CSR activities in international firms results in technological transfer. In other words, stronger links facilitate technology transfer between hotels concerned with CSR and communities in host nations.
- Environmental CSR programs are critical for fostering human well-being, preserving environmental integrity, and conserving the environment and natural resources. This involves the availability and accessibility of dependable resources such as clean air and water, as well as adequate livelihoods.
- CSR encourages a corporation's and the community's interdependence. In other words, a tighter relationship between a firm and the community is another component of CSR's function in community development because it leads to long-term development. Businesses are supposed to be responsible corporate citizens. To acquire this good corporate citizenship emblem, corporations/companies must conduct their activities in accordance with the key principles of sustainable development.
- A CSR program might be viewed as a tool to poverty alleviation. This makes it critical for managers and employees to participate in volunteer and charitable activities in their areas especially in projects that improve the quality of life in a community.
- CSR projects on community development that are successfully implemented stimulate growth, reduce poverty, and are financially advantageous to society's members.
- Multinational corporations, such as Shell and Cisco Systems, construct new branches and operate in developing nations to create job opportunities for locals and to minimize poverty-related unemployment. This condition enhances their socioeconomic status naturally.

CSR activities of leading Hotels in Nigeria: The case of Transcorp Hilton Abuja

Ampofo (2020) claims that hotels, a service-based sector of the economy, have contributed significantly to the growth of the service sector. In order to promote local and regional economic growth, the author emphasized that hotels offer opportunities for direct, indirect,

and induced employment and income at the community level. A good example is the work of Transcorp Hilton Abuja, a renowned hotel chain in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) that received recognition for supporting youth development by working with it to strengthen young people's abilities. The "Business Empowerment Program for Women" was launched by Transcorp Hilton hotel with the primary goal of empowering young local women with fundamental sewing, business start-up, and management skills. This initiative was also driven by the desire to provide jobs for Nigerian youth.

A week-long Career Fair and an internship program for secondary school students were sponsored by the hotel as part of events honoring Hilton World Wide's Youth in Hospitality Month. These achievements in community development were made possible through partnerships. Young Nigerians are taught the fundamentals of cooking and kitchen management as part of the Kitchen Apprenticeship Programme, which is aimed at developing them into chefs of the highest caliber. The chef selected as the best at the end of the program is given the opportunity to work for the Hilton chain, which is thought to be just and noble given the importance of community development. On July 18, 2017, the Transcorp Hilton Abuja's Staff came together to work with ACE Africa Charity to rebuild classrooms, disinfect the surroundings, and create a horticultural garden at Durumi Community Primary School as a way to honor the memory of the iconic Nelson Mandela. Their Team Members, who were motivated by Nelson Mandela's life and times, renovated the run-down school.

Challenges in Implementing Corporate Social Responsibility

- It is undeniable that Nigeria's efforts to implement CSR have run into a number of issues. Ugwunwanyi and Ekene (2016), as cited in Etekpe, (2021), have listed these issues in the following order: a lack of enabling laws to ensure CSR practice, corruption, a lack of enthusiasm for doing so, a lack of benefits or nonexistence of benefits, and political and social instability. They argued that the federal government had not passed any explicit legislation to implement CSR since it first appeared in Nigeria. According to Hakeem Ijaiya (2014), there hasn't been a law established by the Nigerian government for hotels in the domain of corporate social responsibility (CSR) since CSR first took off in Nigeria. The hotels are still free to decide how to handle this. Businesses cannot be held solely accountable for their social obligations to the local communities.
- A lack of community participation in CSR initiatives. According to Ikhana (2022), the local population is generally uninterested in participating in and funding corporate social responsibility projects. Since there have been few efforts to increase awareness of CSR and build public confidence in such initiatives, this may in part be attributable to a lack of knowledge of CSR in the local populations. Lack of contact between corporations and grassroots communities makes the problem worse.

- Uncertainty on both a social and political level. One of the main drivers for firms (domestic or foreign) to conduct business in a nation is the availability of political and social security. Political and social security issues are prevalent in most developing countries (particularly in Africa),
- Insecurity on a social and political level. One of the main drivers for firms (domestic or foreign) to conduct business in a nation is the availability of political and social security. Businesses may find it challenging to participate in CSR due to the political and social unrest that is looming in most developing countries (especially in Africa), which will hurt stakeholders and the organization as a whole (Etekpe, 2021)
- There are either no or very little benefits. Social responsibility ought to benefit both the company and the community. The result, nevertheless, typically benefits the associated enterprise. Businesses contribute a little sum to community projects, then use that money to sell their brands and gain access to markets across the nation (Etekpe, 2021). In socially conscious businesses, the advantages of public relations and brand marketing far outweigh the costs.
- Corruption and selfishness are additional issues with CSR efforts (Osemeke et al., 2016). The majority of nations, especially those in Africa, have an abundance of both natural and human resources. Due to this, the nation's draw the operations of multinational firms that explore these resources in an effort to increase national wealth and alter the economic and social climate for the benefit of the community. Most of these businesses define in their policies the obligation to provide some social benefits to the people they have an impact on through their CSR, in addition to increasing the nation's wealth. It is awful that the prevalence of corruption in most African nations significantly hinders these businesses from embracing CSR (Ekene, 2016) when funds intended for using CSR to improve the lives of society's citizens wind up in the hands of executives who have no regard for ethics or compassion.
- Ikhana (2022) also made the assumption that businesses with a focus on developing nations have voiced concerns about local implementing agencies' lack of transparency because they don't make enough of an effort to disclose information about their programs, audits, and the use of funds intended for CSR activities.

3. Theoretical Models

Many explanations have been proposed by researchers to explain why corporations/companies willingly engage in CSR initiatives. The stakeholder theory, the legitimacy theory, and the political economy theory are some of the theories. According to the legitimacy theory, organizations engage in CSR willingly to demonstrate that they are complying to the expectations and values of the society in which they operate. According to political economics theory, organizations engage in CSR to build a political structure that will

benefit their private interests in the long term. The ideas of the stakeholder theory underpin the hotel's corporate social responsibility and influence on community development in Adamawa Metropolis. As more organizations became aware of the importance of including corporate social responsibility (CSR) features into their planning efforts, Freeman's (1984) key work helped to build the Stakeholder theory. Although there have been few empirical findings demonstrating adopting CSR-related conduct leads to greater financial performance, it has been argued from the beginning that CSR may significantly contribute to a firm's overall performance and the objectives of the firm's stakeholders, including the community. Given its superiority over the other CSR models stated above, this model was chosen for this investigation. According to the stakeholder view, organizations engage in CSR activities because there is an ethical obligation on them to do so, as well as the necessity to manage public opinion significant stakeholders that could exert a harmful impact on organisation. Regardless of the theories mentioned above, the paper contends that the main reason why organizations have chosen to engage in CSR is due to the ethical consideration that it is in their best interests to contribute to healthy societies, ecosystems, and economies, as well as the economic consideration that CSR will improve the organizations' long-run position.

4. Empirical Literature

Samer et al., (2018) conducted research on "the Role of Corporate Social Responsibility in Local Community Development: A Case Study of Jordan Ahli Bank." The research looked at how the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Bank (JAB) can help the local community in Amman, Jordan's capital. The study attempted to investigate how the JAB and the local community perceive CSR as a vehicle for community development. This study employed qualitative research techniques such as semi-structured interviews, media archive and document analysis. This study included a total of (12) individuals, of which (5) were community members, (3) were community leaders, and (4) were JAB public relations participants. Findings show that JAB maintain a high social responsibility sense toward local community.

Etekpe (2021) conducted research on "The Challenges and Benefits of Corporate Social Responsibility in Nigeria: A Study of Bayelsa State Education Development Trust Fund (EDTF) The study analyzed the Fund's level of CSR implementation and the challenges/benefits thereof. It used the Gray, et al (1995) political economics framework and a secondary way of data collecting, which was supplemented by "participant-observation" and focused group discussions (FGD) techniques. The investigation discovered that the Fund had not implemented nor enforced its CSR, and it proposed that the Etekpe's model of CSR measuring index be adapted to monitor and enforce compliance. The implication is that specific

legislation on CSR practice is urgently needed to improve corporate governance in the states and country

Dakare et al., (2011) did a study on "Corporate social responsibility and community development". The study looked into the role of corporate social responsibility in community development. They used a descriptive survey research design. The study's participants included 200 people. Non-probability sampling was employed to select responders with a fair understanding of the subject. A questionnaire was created and utilized to collect information from respondents; the information gathered was evaluated using percentages and the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. According to the study's findings, corporate social responsibility has a major impact on community development. As a result, it was proposed that organizations build an internal climate or orientation that supports corporate social responsibility in community development, as this will enhance firm and community development in diverse areas.

Kumari et al. (2017) also conducted a study titled "Corporate Social Responsibility Activities and their Effect on the Community: A Case Study of Ambuja Cement." The report examined Ambuja Cement Ltd.'s various CSR initiatives in regard to the local community and assessed the impact of those practices on the local community. To achieve this goal, the perspectives and expectations of the community on the company's corporate social responsibility procedures were gathered through focus group talks and a standardized questionnaire. The most educated member of each family in the community was included in the sample. In gathering feedback on perceptions and expectations of CSR, the mining area of the Ambuja Cement factory was also taken into account. The impact of CSR activities was assessed qualitatively and quantitatively, and the results revealed that the community surrounding Ambuja was not well aware of the Company's Act in relation to corporate social responsibility; thus, the study suggested the need to develop good communication policies to raise community awareness.

David (2012) performed a similar study on the "assessment of the influence of corporate social responsibility on Nigerian society: Examples from the banking and telecom industries." The research method was descriptive as well as analytical. Data for the study were gathered from both primary and secondary sources, with a heavy reliance on pertinent information available from the banking and communication industries, as well as other sources. Both regression and correlation analysis were used in the tests. The results demonstrated a strong and significant association between CSR and Societal Development, such that the relationship is statistically significant. According to the study, CSR plays an important part in Societal Progressiveness in terms of environmental and economic progress.

5. Research Methodology

The research approach used included the use of secondary data, which entailed analysis of the already published literature of several studies, papers, magazines, and books pertinent to the topic of study, forming the theoretical foundation of this article. This study analyzes a hypothesis that would allow hotels in the study area to enforce the adoption of CSR in order to improve and elevate the lives of its people in addition to theorizing about the topic under investigation.

Study area

The socio-economic activities of the northeast have been endangered by the occurrence of insurgency, and the insecurity brought on by the insurgency has significantly reduced socio-economic activity in Adamawa state (Ojo et al., 2018). Attacks by Boko Haram have a wide range of negative repercussions that affect every element of life, particularly in the study region. Many rural areas in the states of Borno, Yobe, and Adamawa—the Boko Haram insurgency's epicenter—have been made hazardous for human habitation, driving hundreds of thousands of farmers off their land. It is important to keep in mind that most farmers in Northern Nigeria live in rural areas, which were also the hardest devastated by the Boko Haram insurgency (Musa Shalangwa and Chijioke Kelechi Iwuamadi, 2021). According to recent estimates, the violence has resulted in roughly 17,000 deaths and 2.5 million displacements (Shettima, 2016). Several types of livelihood activities, including agricultural output, have been negatively impacted by this. The Boko Haram insurgency has further sown the seeds of suffering in a region notorious for its crippling poverty, aridity, and recurrent cycle of drought and hunger (Shettima, 2016). The need for hotels to engage in CSR for community development is relevant in light of the significant suffering in the research area. The study's geographic focus was on hotels in Adamawa Metropolis. Yet, the study took into account how CSR affects community development in its whole context. In light of the significant role that hotel development does play in community development in Adamawa state and the difficulties they encounter in implementing CSR, it is essential to conduct a thorough analysis of the contributions of hotels to the growth of the country and their operational challenges.

Figure 1: Administrative Map of Adamawa State showing the 21 local governments

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

The numerous literature reviews revealed that CSR is a necessary tool for community development. CSR encourages corporations to consider the interests of communities by providing social infrastructure such as schools, hospitals, roads, and water supply in their areas of operation. As a result, over time, the concept of CSR has come to be universally regarded as a best practice. Today, the majority of governments, international development organizations, trade associations, academic institutions, and non-governmental organizations recognize that development that benefits all stakeholders, addresses serious and urgent issues such as extreme poverty, and preserves the priceless natural and man-made resources on which human prosperity is based cannot take place unless sustainability is achieved.

The necessity for hotels to embrace CSR is pressing because the study region has been devastated by insurgency attacks. Nonetheless, CSR in Nigeria is still in its infancy. Corporate

enterprises must make an effort to apply it effectively. To meet the objectives set for CSR activities, hotel organizations must take the development of their host communities seriously. This will result in long-term profit maximization and a successful corporate image.

As a result of greater education and media effect, consumers in most developed countries are now aware of corporations' obligations. As a result, corporations or commercial organizations may no longer be able to ignore CSR. Companies' duties in society are no longer just focused on generating profits, but also on acting responsibly toward the larger community.

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations were made:

- Hotels should work with local governments to identify areas of opportunity for enhancing people's lives through the provision of some social amenities. This will greatly raise people's living standards.
- In addition, hotels should involve community residents in the planning, conceptualization, implementation, and evaluation of CSR projects. This will eliminate stakeholder disagreement in some places.
- States and local governments should establish an enabling political and social environment to encourage hotels in their particular communities to engage in long-term social responsibility in order to improve the lives of local residents.
- A proper monitoring system should be put in place to address the issue of marginal and non-existent benefits. This can be accomplished by striking a balance between profit maximization and community benefit. It is critical to recall that CSR necessitates a shift in focus away from the aim of maximizing shareholder value (a profit-driven calculation) and toward the goal of enhancing society wealth (which is a morally based calculation).
- To ensure the effectiveness of hotel CSR, government entities participating in its implementation and enforcement must uphold a high moral and ethical standard. The same is true for the relevant Ministry and other authorities in charge of enforcing environmental legislation.
- The same is true for the relevant Ministry and other institutions in most developing nations tasked with enforcing environmental laws, which should be adequately funded to deal with the government's actions.
- Governments and municipalities should look into places where hotels will pay a set amount of tax to fund community-based projects such as schools, energy, clean water, jobs, and income-generating activities. This could be information about tax breaks. This will inspire hotels to be more responsible at work while also contributing considerably to national growth.

7. Limitation of the study

The study acknowledges a few shortcomings, but they actually lay the groundwork for additional research. Only the metropolis of Adamawa and CSR initiatives that exclusively target the community as a stakeholder are included in the study's purview. So, future research should include all of Adamawa State's local government areas and consider additional elements that relate to customers, employees, suppliers, and other stakeholders. Also, the community served as the analysis' unit. Therefore, it is crucial to research and assess how various stakeholders see CSR projects.

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